

Terpenoids : Part LXXXIX. New Syntheses of Perillene and Dendrolasin

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3-(3-Furyl) propanol (VII), obtained by a four Collins step procedure for two carbons homologation from 3-furylmethanol (III), was oxidised with Collin's reagent to 3-(3-furyl) propanal (VIII). Wittig reaction with isopropylidetriphenylphosphorane on aldehyde (VIII) provided perillene (I).

Grignard reaction of isopropenyl magnesium bromide on (VIII) furnished allyl alcohol (IX) which was converted into its vinyl ether (X) and subsequent pyrolysis of (X) afforded aldehyde (XI). The aldehyde (XI) was subjected to Wittig reaction with isopropylidetriphenylphosphorane to yield dendrolasin (II).

TWO furanoid terpenes, perillene(I) and dendrolasin(II) were isolated from different sources¹⁻⁶ and were identified as 2-methyl-5-(3-furyl) pent-2-ene (I) and 2,6-dimethyl-9-(3-furyl) nonan-2, 6-diene (II) through chemical studies and spectral examinations.

The salient feature, in the structure of these furanoid terpenes, is the presence of a side chain at the unusual 3-position of the furan system. Because of this novel feature, these compounds attracted the attention of synthetic organic chemists and consequently a number of syntheses⁷⁻⁹ of these compounds confirming their structure have been recently reported.

In continuation of our synthetic studies,¹⁰⁻¹⁵ based on the application of Wittig reaction for the

fixation of olifinic bonds in the terpenic compounds, we report in this communication new synthesis of perillene(I) and dendrolasin (II) utilizing 3-(3-furyl) propanal (VIII) as common intermediate. The aldehyde (VIII) was procured from 3-furyl methanol (III) by two carbons homologation through a 4-step procedure. It was then tailored to the title compounds through the sequence of well known reactions as depicted below :

3-Furylmethanol (III) was converted into mesylate (IV) by treating with methane-sulphonyl chloride¹⁶ in the presence of triethylamine using dichloromethane as a solvent. Mesylate (IV), without further purification, was reacted with sodium salt of malonic ester in anhydrous benzene¹⁷ to secure the diester (V) in 84.2% yield. One of the carbethoxy groups of the substituted malonic ester (V) was eliminated by heating with NaCl-DMSO¹⁸ when ethyl 3-(3-furyl) propanoate (VI) was obtained in 78.6% yield. The ester(VI) was smoothly reduced with LAH in dry ether to furnish 3-(3-furyl) propanol (VII) in high yield. The primary alcohol (VII) was subsequently oxidised with Collins reagent¹⁹ at room temperature to provide the aldehyde (VIII) in 61% yield which was used as a common intermediate for the syntheses of perillene (I) and dendrolasin (II).

3-(3-Furyl) propanal (VIII) was submitted to Wittig reaction with isopropylidene triphenylphosphorane in DMSO²⁰ to afford perillene. The identity of the synthesised product was substantiated through I. R. and NMR spectra.

Grignard reaction of isopropenyl magnesium bromide on (VIII) provided the allyl alcohol (IX) which was transformed into its vinyl ether (X) through mercuric acetate catalysed trans-etherification with ethyl vinyl ether. Pyrolysis of (X) after purification (column chromatography over alumina using pet ether as an eluent) generated aldehyde (XI) in about 80% yield. Finally the Wittig reaction with isopropylidene triphenyl phosphorane furnished dendrolasin (II) in high yield. The spectral data of the synthetic compound agree with the values reported in literature.

Experimental

Boiling points are uncorrected. I. R. spectra were recorded on a Perkin Elmer, model 337 Infrared spectrophotometer with sodium chloride optics using thin liquid films. NMR spectra were recorded at 60 MHz using TMS as an internal standard.

3-Furylmethanol (III) : The compound was prepared exactly according to the procedure described in the literature²¹.

Ethyl-3-(3-furyl)-1-carbethoxy-propanoate (IV) : Methanesulphonyl chloride (14 g) was added to a mixture of 3-furyl methanol (III, 10 g), methylene chloride (120 ml) and triethylamine (14 g) at -10°

with constant stirring over a period of 20 min. The contents were poured into ice cold water, the organic phase was washed with water and dried (CaCl_2). Evaporation of the solvent gave the crude product (IV, 17 g) which was used as such without further purification for the next operation. Its infrared spectrum showed the absence of any band in the hydroxyl region.

The solution of mesylate (IV, 17 g) in benzene (80 ml) was added to the suspension of the sodium salt of malonic ester (prepared from 2.7 g of sodium and 18.4 g of diethyl malonate) at room temperature and then the reaction mixture was refluxed for 8 hr on a water bath. The contents were cooled, added to ice cold water and organic layer was separated. After removing the solvent the residual oil left was distilled under diminished pressure to give diester (V), b. p. $140^{\circ}\text{--}145^{\circ}/5$ mm, yield 14.2 g (84%). ν_{max} : 2950, 1735, 1600, 1510, 1445, 1350, 1260, 1170, 1155, 1105, 1050, 1020, 950, 889, 790 and 735 cm^{-1} . (Found : C, 60.2 ; H, 6.60 ; $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 60.0 ; H, 6.71%).

Ethyl-3 (3-furyl) propanoate (VI) : A mixture of diester (V, 12.0 g), sodium chloride (3.6 g), dimethylsulphoxide (100 ml) and water (5 ml) was heated at 160° for 4 hr. The contents were cooled, added to cold water and extracted with ether. The combined organic phase was washed with water and dried. The residue left after the removal of the solvent was vacuum distilled to produce monoester (IV) yield 6.6 g (78.6%), b. p. $100^{\circ}\text{--}05^{\circ}/6$ mm. ν_{max} : (2970, 1720, 1620, 1510, 1450, 1380, 1350, 1300, 1260, 1160, 1060, 1030, 950, 930, 875, 790 and 740 cm^{-1} . (Found : C, 64.15 ; H, 7.2 ; $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 64.27 H, 7.19%).

3-(3-Furyl) propanol (VII) : A fine suspension of LAH (1.92 g) in dry ether (200 ml) was placed in a two necked flask fitted with a dropping funnel, a reflux condenser (protected by a guard tube) and equipped with a magnetic stirrer. To this was added during stirring, the ester (VI, 6.0 g) in anhydrous ether (100 ml) so as to keep ether at a gentle reflux. After the addition was over, the reaction mixture was stirred continuously for 8 hr and left overnight. There after the reaction mixture was cooled and poured into ice cold solution of sodium potassium tartrate. The product was extracted with ether, washed with water and dried. Evaporation of the solvent and subsequent distillation of the residue under reduced pressure gave alcohol (VII), b. p. $115^{\circ}\text{--}20^{\circ}/8$ mm, yield 4 g (80%). ν_{max} : 3350, 1600, 1500, 1450, 1350, 1165, 1100, 1050, 1030, 950, 880, 790 and 735 cm^{-1} . (Found : C, 66.55 ; H, 7.91 ; $\text{C}_7\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 66.64 ; H, 7.99%).

3-(3-Furyl) propanal (VIII) : Chromium trioxide (9 g) was added in small instalments to well cooled dry pyridine (14.5 ml) and methylene chloride (60 ml) with stirring. The yellow coloured complex thus obtained was stirred for an additional 15 min at

room temperature. The alcohol (VII, 1.9 g) in methylene chloride (10 ml) was added to it. A black tar deposited immediately with the evolution of heat. The stirring was continued thereafter at 20° for 30 min and put into crushed ice. The organic layer was washed with water and dried (CaCl₂). The solvent was removed and the residue was distilled under reduced pressure to produce aldehyde (VIII), b. p. 90°-95°/10 mm, yield 1.1 g (61%). ν_{\max} . 2950, 2710, 1710, 1660, 1450, 1370, 1300, 1230, 1160, 1030, 875, 790 and 735 cm⁻¹. (Found : C, 67.62 ; H, 6.94 ; C₇H₈O₂ Requires : C, 67.73 ; H, 6.50%).

2, 4-DNP, prepared from sulphuric acid method, melted at 118°. (Found : N, 18.38 ; C₁₃H₁₂N₄O₅ Requires : N, 18.42%).

2-Methyl-5-(3-furyl) pent-2-ene (I) : A solution of sodium dimethyl sulphanyl was prepared from NaH (240 mg) and DMSO (2.4 ml). This on treatment with isopropyltriphenylphosphonium iodide (2.16 g) in DMSO (4.8 ml) formed a red coloured phosphorane. After stirring it for 10 min at room temperature, aldehyde (VIII, 500 mg) in tetrahydrofuran (2 ml) was added, stirring was continued for 4 hr at room temperature and left overnight. The contents were poured into ice cold water and aqueous was extracted with petroleum ether (3 × 40 ml). The combined organic phase was dried and solvent was removed. The crude residual oil was purified by column chromatography over neutral alumina using petroleum ether as an eluent and distillation under diminished pressure to afford perillene (I), b. p. 95°-100°/5 mm, yield 450 mg (70%). ν_{\max} 2950, 1600, 1500, 1450, 1400, 1260, 1160, 1110, 1080, 1020, 1000 940, 875, 790 and 740 cm⁻¹.

NMR spectrum showed signals at τ : 2.78 (2H, furan) 3.76 (1H, d, furan), 4.76 (1H, olefin), 7.68-7.8 (4H, allylic methylene) and 8.36 (6H, d, methyl on double bond). (Found : C, 79.87 ; H, 9.41 ; C₁₀H₁₄O Requires : C, 79.95 ; H, 9.39%).

2-Methyl-3-hydroxy-5-(3-furyl) pent-1-ene (IX) : To the Grignard reagent, prepared from magnesium (3 g) and isopropenyl bromide (15 g) in dry THF (200 ml), was added dropwise a solution of aldehyde (VIII, 6.4 g) in THF (20 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred well for 2 hr and left overnight at room temperature. It was then decomposed with a saturated solution of ammonium chloride and worked up in the usual manner. Removal of the solvent and the distillation of the residue gave (IX) as a colourless oil, b. p. 95°-100°/7 mm ; yield 5.8 g (68.68%) ν_{\max} . 3350, 3060, 1640, 1450, 1350, 1230, 1170, 1150, 1045, 1010, 875, 790 and 735 cm⁻¹. (Found : C, 72.08 ; H, 8.68 ; C₁₀H₁₄O₂ Requires : C, 72.26 ; H, 8.49%).

2-Methyl-3-vinyloxy-5-(3-Furyl) pent-1-ene (X) : A mixture of alcohol (IX, 4 g), ethyl vinyl ether (40 ml) and freshly crystallised mercuric acetate (800 mg) was heated under reflux for 16 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled in ice cold bath and

stirred for 30 min with cold sodium carbonate solution (10%, 50 ml). The organic phase was separated washed with water and dried (K₂CO₃). The excess vinyl ether was evaporated and the residue on chromatography over neutral alumina furnished the vinyl ether (X) which was further purified by distillation under reduced pressure. The pure vinyl ether (X) b. p. 80°-85°/10 mm ; yield 3.4 g (62%). ν_{\max} 3060, 1640, 1625, 1460, 1350, 1175, 1045, 885, 790 and 735. cm⁻¹. (Found : C, 74.54 ; H, 8.52 ; C₁₂H₁₆O₂ Requires : C, 74.97 ; H, 8.39%).

4-Methyl-7-(3-furyl)-4-eneheptanal (XI) : The vinyl ether (3 g) was heated for 30 min at 175° in an atmosphere of nitrogen in a half filled sealed tube, fully immersed, in an oil bath. Direct distillation afforded the aldehyde (XI) b. p. 98°-101°/10 mm, yield 2.5 g (83%). ν_{\max} . 2710, 1720, 1640, 1450, 1150, 1045, 965, 885, 790 and 735 cm⁻¹. (Found : C, 74.68 ; H, 8.48 ; C₁₂H₁₆O₂ Requires : C, 74.97 ; H, 8.39%). 2, 4-DNP, derivative melted at 126°. (Found : N, 14.96 ; C₁₈H₂₀O₅N₄ Requires : N, 15.05%).

2, 6-Dimethyl-9-(3-furyl)-2, 6-nonadiene (II) : A solution of methyl sulphanyl carbanion was prepared under nitrogen atmosphere as usual, from sodium hydride (500 mg) and dimethyl sulphoxide (5 ml). This on treatment with isopropyltriphenylphosphonium iodide (4.5 g) in DMSO (10 ml) in cold gave deep red coloured phosphorane. The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 10 min. To this was added the aldehyde (XI, 1.5 g) in THF (5 ml). The contents were stirred for 2 hr and then left overnight at room temperature. The contents were poured in crushed ice and worked up as usual. The crude product obtained after removal of solvent was chromatographed over alumina with benzene-pet ether (1:9) and was further purified by distillation under diminished pressure to produce dendrolasin (II), b. p. 110°-15°/8 mm, yield 1.2 g (65%). ν_{\max} . 2940, 1620, 1600, 1510, 1450, 1400, 1260, 1180, 1110, 1080, 1010, 960, 875, 790 and 740 cm⁻¹.

60 MHz exhibited signals at τ : 2.72 (2H, d, furan), 3.78 (1H, d, furan), 4.76 (2H, olefin), 7.6-8.0 (8H, allylic methylene) and 8.3-8.42 (9H, methyl on double bond). (Found : C, 82.47 ; H, 10.24 ; C₁₅H₂₂O Requires : C, 82.51 ; H, 10.16%).

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